

Exploring the Flight from Nepali Ethnic Identity in Manjushree Thapa's *Seasons of Flight*

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Nepal, the small Himalayan nation, has long served as the picturesque land of beautiful snow peaked mountains, scenic landscapes. In spite of that beautiful nature, one is unable to forget the fact that the denizens of the nation remained for long under the shadow of the civil war (1996-2006). The theme of war and trauma has been a recurring theme in many literary works. Manjushree Thapa, has been no exception to this phenomenon. Considered as the foremost diasporic voice of Nepal, Thapa in her novel *Seasons of Flight* does not present the topographic beauty of Nepal, rather she presents the geo-political scenario and the situational

reality which compel her protagonist Prema to fly away from her native land. An individual sense of identity is intertwined with the calamitous impact of trauma. War in the native land can create trauma as it effects the psyche of an individual. The harrowing impact of trauma can create a sense of disconnection from one's ethnic identity. As ethnic identity is a social form of identity, it incorporates various factors like social issues, cultural experiences, religious practices and personal beliefs. Ethnic identity also denotes a person's sense of belonging to an ethnic group. Ethnic identity can evolve over time. Political conflicts in any nation are major reasons for people's dispersion, as the conflict zones fail to provide better hopes and opportunities for the people. They become more hopeless after witnessing hatred and violence. When Prema was working in an NGO in hill bazar, the rise of Maoist uprising in her native land jeopardised her sense of safety and security. It also reduced the chance of economic prosperity in Nepali society. In this backdrop, the computer shop owner Kancha who was Prema's neighbour was arrested and disappeared. Prema was deeply affected by this particular event as "Kancha's abduction disheartened Prema, and made her withdraw into herself" (Thapa 2012, 63). Not only the war in Nepal but the narrow religious practices, cultural experiences in Nepal also traumatize the protagonist Prema. She feels suffocation in her own land. She tries to escape from her ethnic identity and reconstruct a new identity in a new land.

The Maoist insurgency in Nepal disrupted people's life and increased tensions among people in Nepal. When the Maoist rebels came in the village, they forced other people to join with them. Prema's sister Bijaya also joined in the war. This war actually shatters Prema's psyche and prompts her to think about escaping from her ethnic identity. The violence of war, especially Kancha's disappearance makes her realise the truth: "Prema was convinced the war would escalate from here on. The Maoists would not give up, [...] people who had nothing to do with either side would get drawn in" (Thapa 2012, 66). She suffers from a dilemma and thinks "Should she not leave? This shabby, Third World country" (Thapa 2012, 66). The war had confounded her mental state. Her thinking of war and her previous encounter with the Maoists scar her mind as "she recalled, with revulsion, the soldier who had asked her for identification" (Thapa 2012, 66) and she started to think "What if the Maoists were to come here, as they had to her birth village? She kept feeling a shivering in the marrow" (Thapa 2012, 66). The trauma and the violence of war lead to the subsequent flight of people in search of peace and better opportunities.

Prema sets out on a journey in order to escape from her Nepali ethnic identity and her native land that is infested with Maoist aggression. Prema moves to America and she tries to adjust herself and create a new identity in

a new land. After arriving in America, she starts to live in “Little Nepal” in Virginia (Thapa 2012,108) where many people of the Nepali community live in America. But unlike most immigrants who prefer a close attachment with their own people in a foreign land, Prema believes that her relationship with them actually has kept her outside America. Their companionship reminds Prema about her own ethnic country and thereby, it makes Prema to retain her Nepali ethnic identity from which she wants to escape. Their companionship immobilises Prema’s search for new identity as “she felt stuck on the outside of America [...] and their talk invariably turned homeward: the Maoist rebels, the king and the army, the faltering movement for peace” (Thapa 2012, 112). But Prema wanted to see what lay beyond Little Nepal and reinvent herself in America.

Prema’s quest for adopting American identity forces her to cut off contact with home and “she stopped looking up the news of Nepal on the Internet, and let her email account expire” (Thapa 2012, 116). She disconnects her connection with fellow Nepali migrants Neeru and Sushil in order to escape from her Nepali identity and create a cosmopolitan identity in a multicultural society in America. “Prema left Little Nepal as abruptly as she had left Nepal” (Thapa 2012, 117) and she goes far away from the Nepalese circle of Sushil and Neeru as to become a complete American. She strives to create her identity in a foreign land through acculturation. To

be Americanized, she mimics American people and she buys a red bikini and flip-flops. “Mimicking them she jumped as the water level rose; she jumped again when it rose again” (Thapa 2012, 79 and 80). Prema feels sexually liberated in America and enjoys her body. Sexual liberation was something unimaginable in the Nepali culture. While in Nepal she had to keep her relationship with Rajan secret, in America she has casual sexual encounters with different men. As part of this acculturation she also attends Thanksgiving and Christmas ceremony in Luis’s family gathering. By mimicking American culture, she turns into a hybridized entity. In Bhabha’s terms, the discourse of mimicry “is constructed around ambivalence” (Bhabha 1994, 86). Prema’s state in a foreign land is quite ambiguous. As a girl from Third World country Prema feels the superiority of First World country like America. She, therefore, tries to adopt American culture by mimicking their ways and customs. Though she is trying to fly away from her ethnic identity, but she cannot find a sense of satisfaction in the host country as her memory keeps haunting her. As Khem Guragaini points out “Prema, therefore, remains unfulfilled and torn between her past life in Nepal and her newly discovered ‘confused’ life in America” (Guragaini 2014, 63). Jane Fernandez in her article “Framing the Diaspora: Politics of Identity and Belonging” argues:

The several definitions of diaspora: whether involving the dispersion of a classical group/people, or

forced dislocation from the homeland, or voluntary migration, or indicating an attachment to multiple nations/histories, has one thing in common. In all these varying categories, the underlying premise that girds the issues of diaspora involves concepts of identity and belonging.(29)

Prema wants to rebuild a new identity. But Prema faces many problems in trying to assimilate American culture. She experiences a psychological state of ambiguous or in-betweenness. To embrace American culture “Prema has to undergo a cultural transformation in order to embrace American culture, and assert herself and identity” (Guragaini 2014, 64). She faces various difficulties and keeps drifting from one place to another. Her dream of fulfilling her desires through an escape from her ethnic identity results in a kind of botched cosmopolitanism that ends up stunting her growth.

Thapa’s novel also problematizes the Hindu Nepali identity through the protagonist Prema who is a girl from war ravaged village of Nepal. Being brought up in a typical Hindu religious background in a distant village of Nepal, she notices the faithful devotion of Nepali women to the Hindu religion and its practices. She remembers how her mother used to worship ammonite which is believed as an incarnation of Vishnu, a god of protection. Prema visits the temple of Mata Sylvia in America. There she notices the books of her own religion such as the *Bhaga-*

Upanishad Gita, the *Mahabharat*, the *Ramayana*, and books about Osho, Krishnamurti, Vivekananda, Ram Das, Sai Baba, Aurobindo, Maharishi Mahesh Yogi and she realizes that “It was the kind of place in which Prema’s mother would have sought refuge” (Thapa 2012, 179). But Prema herself does not find any refuge in her own religious culture. Rather it provokes Prema to fly away from her own ethnic identity where women are subjugated in the name of religion. When Mata Sylvia was speaking about the divine love, “Prema did not feel this love. Instead, she recalled her mother’s bedroom shrine, crowded with the gods: Krishna, Parvati, Shiva, Laksmi, the avatar of Bishnu in a fossil” (Thapa 2012, 180). She wonders that though her mother passionately devoted herself to the Hindu god and its rituals but “Had it made her feel safe? Even as her love for Prema’s father made her lose her life?” (Thapa 2012, 180).

Religious scripture plays a vital role to shape people’s thought and perception. When people follow a religion, its customs and rituals also become a part of their culture. In Nepali culture it was believed that “Only a son can open the gates of heaven” (Thapa 2012, 181). Therefore, Nepali orthodox parents desire to have a son so that their death ritual can be performed and their soul can be liberated after death. Prema’s parents had also wanted a son which brought about the untimely death of her mother and Prema witnessed it when she was a child. This event terribly injured her mind and “The

wounds of childhood, relics around which deposits have hardened, adamantine” (Thapa 2012, 15). She recalls this bitter incident in her conversation with her American boyfriend Luis: “She kept getting pregnant because she wanted a son! [...] one baby before me, two afterwards- they all died. And she- All she wanted was a son!” (Thapa 2012, 183). It is this scriptural misogyny that makes Prema hostile to Hindu religion. Religion is an important factor in all culture. Sachedina remarked that “Throughout history, women have been denied basic human rights, through religiously imposed restrictions or economically designed exploitation and manipulation of their position in family and in society” (Sachedina 2003, 11). In Prema’s understanding the scriptural text of *Manusmriti* also ascribes an inferior position on women and relegates them to be a mere slave as is evident in Prema’s statement “The book where it says women are slaves” (Thapa 2012, 183).

Nepali religious culture and her own ethnic identity that causes her mother’s death, traumatize Prema’s psyche. When a traumatic experience takes place, it changes the way a person thinks. It may lead to post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) which develops in some persons who have experienced a shocking, scary, or dangerous event. Prema’s mother’s death during childbirth shocked Prema very much. The trauma of child birth affects Prema’s intimate relationships both with Rajan in Nepal and Luis in America. She seeks fulfilment therefore in

casual sexual encounters without being bound by the institutions of marriage and motherhood. Her trauma makes compels her to escape from the emotions and institutions responsible for such trauma. Therefore, she wants to escape from the idea of childbirth: “Although well into the age of an arranged marriage, Prema had no desire to find a husband. A dread seeped through her at the thought of childbirth. She had seen it consume her mother” (Thapa 2012, 55). Her trauma tends to dissociate herself from the experience that is associated with her trauma. Prema also tells her boyfriend Luis that “I have never wanted to have children. Having children is dangerous” (Thapa 2012, 250). She does not want to follow her mother’s path who is a representation of typical Nepali woman and “In no way had she replicated her mother’s life” (Thapa 2012, 55). Rather she flies away into an alienated land by rejecting her typical Nepali ethnic identity. Berman, Montgomery, and Ratner in their article “Trauma and identity: A reciprocal relationship?” remarked that “Trauma can alter the course of identity development and destabilize existing identity commitments. Trauma, whether past or current, can also impact the resources a person brings to identity work” (Berman, Montgomery, and Ratner 2020, 31).

As an uneducated woman Prema’s mother is affected by the religious indoctrination and the typical notion of Nepali country. What is surprising is that the educated people also cannot liberate their mind. Prema notices

how a school teacher makes arrangement of marriage for her eighteen years old daughter. The school teacher couple called themselves progressive but they prepare her daughter's wedding after her passing out of high school. Further when their daughters became pregnant, the girl's mother says "If it's a son, her in-laws won't pressure her to have more children" (Thapa 2012, 60). Prema realises that both the educated people and the uneducated people are similarly interpellated by patriarchal discourses and attendant privileging of male children. It makes her realise that the spread of education in Nepal has not yet brought changes in the mind of the people who continue to remain grossly affected by gender discrimination. She, therefore, tries to evade her ethnic identity which hinders her development. It is in this way that traumatic events can cause a person to re-evaluate his/her identity.

Prema's lifestyle in America is interrupted by her traumatic memory from the past. Unlike other diasporic protagonists, she does not recollect the sweet memory of her homeland. When Prema learns about the war in Guatemala from her boyfriend Luis, she moves back to her own past. It actually brings forth her traumatic memory of war in Nepal which had been repressed. She tells Luis that "the war in Guatemala is like the war at home" (Thapa 2012, 172). The recollection of the fearful memory makes people more traumatic. In *Studies on Hysteria*, Breuer and Freud said that "Hysterics suffer mainly from

reminiscences” (Breuer and Freud 1966, 7). Prema becomes more eager to know more about Guatemala. She is curious to know about the refugees of the Guatemala war. When she learns from Luis about the disappearance and killing of two hundred thousand people, she was shocked. However, Luis’s mind was not affected as much as Prema’s mind was affected by the picture of the Guatemalans. This is due to Prema’s previous encounter with a similar kind of war. The memory of Maoist insurgency in Nepal deeply lacerates her mind. In *Trauma: Explorations in Memory*, Caruth highlights the traumatic return and says that it is the “insistent return which thus constitutes trauma and points toward its enigmatic core” (Caruth 1995, 5). It is Prema’s return to the corrosive Maoist war in Nepal that constitutes her trauma.

As Prema had faced the similar kind of war-like situation in her native land, her reminiscence triggers post-traumatic stress disorder. Prema frequently visits library and each time she looked up more on Guatemala and “The more Prema found about Guatemala, the more she wanted to find out” (Thapa 2012, 163). She remembers the war in her early life by learning about the war in other people’s lives. As she is suffering from post-traumatic stress disorder, she repeatedly relives her past days through thoughts and memories. Prema indulges in the thought of her father, her sister Bijaya who had joined in Maoist rebel movement, and the boy Kancha who was dragged to the police custody before disappearing.

When she is thinking about all these “She felt an ancient shivering in the marrow” (Thapa 2012, 168) which she had earlier felt during the war in her home country. This stirring of memorial past about her ethnic lands serves as the breach in her present diurnal existence. It startles her present life in her host land America. She was haunted by her severe memory: “Nepal was haunting her through tricks of the mind, Guatemala” (Thapa 2012, 203). She dwindles due to her painful memories. She starts to check the internet for news of home and she even calls her father after a long period. But her reminiscence was, however, not of a diasporic individual missing his homeland. It is her original trauma that entangles her in a loop of return and loss.

Being distracted by the memory she leads a nomadic existence and she has a sense of what some might call out-of-placeness. When Luis wanted to see Prema’s world, she cried by saying that “I do not have a world! I left the world I had, and do not belong in the one I am in now- your world” (Thapa 2012, 212). She is searching her path and she feels directionless and she is “tracing her way along her ever-directionless zigzag trail” (Thapa 2012, 216). After a long decade she moves to her birth village in Nepal. But she does not find any solace in Nepal either. She again moves back to America in search of a new life and personal fulfilment. She continually drifts from one place to another.

Identity is not a fixed entity. Ethnic identity which we can say is a social form of identity is also flexible. Circumstantial changes make one's ethnic identity fragile and unsteady. Prema takes a departure from her Nepali ethnic identity because of its socio-political scenario and the claustrophobic religious culture. She flies away from her ethnic land and experiences a world of fluidity and instability. To fit herself into the mainstream American culture, she transforms herself. Her assimilation into a new culture can be seen as a way to overcome the challenges and barriers that one faces in a new land. But it is difficult to erase one's ethnic identity, the inheritance of the past. The traumatic war that makes her fly away from her native land, the memory of that traumatic war again causes her to move back to her homeland. However, she finally returns in America and prefers to live in the liberated American multicultural society.

At the end, Prema settles in America and engages with the El Segundo Blue butterfly conservation. Prema has a resemblance with the transformational process that a butterfly undergoes. Butterfly has different stages of life: egg, caterpillar, pupa, chrysalis, and finally butterfly. The symbolic journey of the butterfly indicates the metamorphosis we all go through. Butterfly reminds us to rely on our transformational process. It can be troublesome and grievous when we outstrip a belief, relationship and habit. The same is true for Prema, she is confused and horrified as she moves from her known

world to a shadowy unknown world. Change is an important factor in life, therefore, Prema needs to let go of her traumatic past in order to create a better future. The cocoon is the comfort zone of the butterfly and if the caterpillar never emerges from this state the process of individualization will never find fruition. Prema flies away from her ethnic identity and her native land to transform into a new individual. Though she feels intense upheaval and uncertainty in the course of the journey, but the shift gives her “wing” to fly forward with confidence.

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